

Dangerous Documents

Approaches to Making Fascist Materials Available

University of Oslo, Department of Philosophy, Classics, and the History of Art and Ideas

21 June 2024, 08:30–18:00

CONFERENCE REPORT

On June 21, 2024, a group of international scholars convened at the University of Oslo to engage in a discussion centred on the cultural and moral ramifications of making historical documents associated with fascist regimes accessible. Representing diverse academic disciplines such as history, art history, classical philology, history of architecture, colonial history, and library and information science, these scholars all had experience with making various kinds of documents from fascist contexts accessible, by different means, in different contexts, and for various audiences. This report seeks to capture some key insights from the conference. It does not provide a comprehensive summary of each individual paper but endeavours to distil the main considerations discussed during the event. The full conference program is available below (see pp. 5-6).

Speakers included, in alphabetical order, Susanna Arangio (University of Ferrara), Patrizia Cacciani (Istituto Luce, Rome), Antonio Duplá Ansuátegui (University of the Basque Country UPV/EHU), Beatrice Falucci (Pompeu Fabra University, Barcelona), Christian Hartmann (Bundeswehr Centre for Military History and Social Sciences), Han Lamers (University of Oslo), Flavia Marcello (Swinburne University's School of Design and Architecture), Gianmarco Mancosu (University of London), and Elisabetta Cassina Wolff (University of Oslo). All speakers were asked to briefly present the types of documents they work with, the ethical challenges they face, and how they address these challenges.

Each paper was followed by lively discussion, in which attendees also participated. The conversations were moderated by Marie-Laurence Haack (University of Picardy Jules Verne), Magnus Pharao Hansen (University of Copenhagen), Han Lamers, and Bettina Reitz-Joosse.

The initial two sessions concentrated on the publication of **textual documents** from Fascist Italy, National Socialist Germany, and Francoist Spain. The first session centred on **printed texts**. Hartmann presented a paper exploring the publication of a key text of German National Socialism, Adolf Hitler's *Mein Kampf*. Lamers and Reitz-Joosse, on the other hand, discussed the publication of a collection of largely unknown Latin texts from Fascist Italy and National Socialist Germany. The second session shifted the discussion from printed pages to inscribed surfaces and examined **inscriptions** associated with fascism regimes that can still be found publicly within some European cityscapes. Marcello's paper explored the difficult legacy of fascist inscriptions in Rome and approaches of re-claiming, ignoring, or removing them. Duplá Ansuátegui explored the situation of the lesser-known Latin inscriptions of Francoist Spain and the associated discussions, highlighting some differences with the Italian context.

The third session, comprising three papers, shifted the focus from textual documents to **material and audiovisual documents**, encompassing Fascist art and memorabilia, as well as

photographs and film. Arangio analyzed the display of Mussolini-related objects in Italian collections, particularly focusing on the MAGI'900 Museum in Pieve di Cento. She highlighted the risk of normalizing the Mussolini cult and emphasized the need for a centralized documentation center on Italian Fascism to raise awareness and calibrate the responsibility of private collectors. Falcucci explored the curatorial challenges in presenting the material culture of Fascist colonies in Italian museums, with a focus on recent initiatives to engage with the material heritage of the colonial past. Taking the Istituto Luce as their starting point, Cacciani and Mancosu (the former *in absentia*) examined the challenges of making Fascist audiovisual materials available for the wider audience.

Wolff's paper on Julius Evola's reception in neo-fascist circles rounded off the meeting, serving as a reminder of how historical documents can still be used to promote harmful ideologies.

Takeaways from the discussions

- The danger associated with making the documents under study accessible often remains implicit and may vary from case to case. Nevertheless, it is essential to define and assess the perceived danger in an explicit way. Specific risks – both perceived and real – with the publication of documents include the dissemination of harmful ideas, the reinforcement of extremist and/or aggressive worldviews, bolstering nostalgic narratives, and causing emotional distress for victims of fascism and their families.
- In many cases, the actual persuasive power of these documents as calls to action appears relatively weak due to their outdated information and limited applicability to modern political contexts. This is consistent with how the societal dangers posed by other historical documents—ranging from *Malleus Maleficarum* to *Die Leiden des jungen Werthers*—have been confined to specific contexts in the past, with their contents seeming relatively harmless today.
- The primary danger of historical documents associated with fascism lies in their potential to become symbolic objects, tokens, or talismans for those who, in some way or another, sympathize with the ideologies they represent. This shift in focus from the documents' content to the contexts of their use highlights that while their content may be objectionable and offensive, their social and cultural danger mainly arises from the ways in which they are employed by proponents of neo-fascism and related ideologies.
- From the discussions, an important distinction emerged between documents that are already in circulation and those that remain hidden and unknown to the wider public. While most would agree that scholars need to address materials already in circulation, including high-profile texts such as *Mein Kampf* and highly visible ones such as inscriptions, the question of unearthing hidden documents is less clear-cut. Although some scepticism was expressed about making materials available that are not currently in circulation, there was a consensus that there should be compelling reasons for withholding historical documents from those with an interest in them.
- To counteract ideological appropriation, it is crucial to establish scholarly ownership over the narratives surrounding the documents. This effort includes academic endeavours such as controlling and questioning half-truths, distortions of reality, and contradictions present

in the documents; deconstructing and explaining their rhetorical strategies; foregrounding the oppressive contexts in which the document was produced and served its purpose, and bringing forth suppressed voices. In the case of unknown documents, presenting them in a scholarly manner can be viewed as a form of ‘pre-emptive publishing.’ For unknown texts susceptible to ideological tokenization, this means releasing scholarly editions before political or ideological interest groups can discover and exploit them to fit their own narratives. For unknown objects and audiovisual materials, this means making them available in thoughtfully curated settings, such as collections, museums, or archives.

- To enhance scholarly control over the narrative, it is important to reach out to non-academic audiences. This can be achieved through various means, including informative pieces, opinion articles in magazines and newspapers, and socio-cultural initiatives such as exhibitions. Based on their experience, participants stressed the importance of developing a professional and well-thought through communication and press strategy to accompany the release or publication of materials (the case of the critical edition of *Mein Kampf* in particular offered a range of best practices for how this can be achieved). Careful planning becomes even more important given the risk of unintentionally contributing to the sensationalism potentially associated with these documents. While some believe it is debatable whether disseminating research results among non-academic audiences falls within the purview of scholars’ responsibilities, most would agree that to enhance scholarly ownership of the narratives surrounding the documents under study, scholars have a certain duty to help make their work publicly known.
- It was widely acknowledged that simply ‘sending’ scholarly information into the public realm is insufficient. Instead, we should engage in dialogue with diverse groups outside academia. Addressing their concerns and questions improves scholarly communication and decision-making, especially on sensitive issues. This is important because, while much academic work caters to an international audience, the documents released can significantly impact local and national communities to which researchers may not belong. It was emphasized that publication must be approached with empathy towards those who might be adversely affected and with an understanding of the ethical and legal aspects relevant to difficult heritage across various countries. For example, visual materials depicting victims of colonialism can have harmful consequences for certain communities and individuals if fully released. Describing the material, rather than publishing it fully, may in such cases reduce harm while still acknowledging the documents’ existence.
- Teaming up with other scholars and reaching out to non-academic audiences is also important, as we may find that institutions such as archives, libraries, and museums are slow to address these materials or may even be reluctant to do so. Reasons for this vary and include lack of resources, uncertainty about appropriate strategies to address the materials, or a fear of inadvertently promoting ‘nostalgic’ narratives. Scholars can play a role in overcoming some of these obstacles and ensuring responsible engagement with historical documents beyond academia.
- Despite calls to enhance scholarly control over the interpretation of challenging historical documents, it was repeatedly stressed that regardless of our scholarly framing and diligent efforts to control the narrative, most documents can be used for any purpose and can potentially be employed in ways that are considered dangerous. Once we release historical

documents, we relinquish full control over how they are appropriated, and we cannot be held accountable for the countless interpretations that may arise. While this might appear discouraging, we must not shirk our responsibility to approach the past in a just and responsible way and to grant people access to the documents they need to comprehend their histories and those of others.

- It was apparent that our discussions were not grounded in a single theoretical framework, and there was no prefabricated vocabulary to share our thoughts and ideas. Each speaker approached the issues with a pragmatic, hands-on approach. The absence of a common conceptual framework suggests that we were pioneering a much-needed discussion. This workshop seems to have been the first international meeting on the topic. Participants expressed their hopes that it would not be the last and that the conversation could be extended and expanded to include other stakeholders in this ongoing debate.

Disclaimer and acknowledgements

The compilation of this report is primarily based on minutes taken by Sunniva Regine Berger, Victoria Cecilie Frivik, Han Lamers, Erlend Østrem Myklebust, and Bettina Reitz-Joosse. A previous version of the report was circulated among workshop participants, and the current text includes their feedback. Statements in the report do not necessarily reflect the opinions of individual participants or its organisers. The corresponding author assumes responsibility for any remaining inaccuracies in representing the discussions.

The conference ‘Dangerous Documents: Approaches to Making Fascist Materials Available’ was organized by the research initiative ‘Language Myths: Towards a Global Approach to the Politicization of Ancient Languages’ (University of Oslo, University of Copenhagen, and University of Picardy Jules Verne), financed by the Fondation Maison des Sciences de l’Homme and the Centre Universitaire de Norvège à Paris, in collaboration with the research projects ‘New Signs of Antiquity’ (University of Oslo), funded by the Research Council of Norway (Grant No. 316016), and ‘Anchoring the Fascist Revolution’ (University of Groningen), supported by OIKOS, the National Research School in Classical Studies in the Netherlands (Gravitation Grant research agenda Anchoring Innovation).

The conveners of the conference were Han Lamers (University of Oslo), Bettina Reitz-Joosse (University of Groningen), Marie-Laurence Haack (University of Picardy Jules Verne), and Magnus Pharaos Hansen (University of Copenhagen).

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Han Lamers

Programme

Dangerous Documents

Approaches to Making Fascist Materials Available

University of Oslo | Friday, 21 June 2024

08:30 Han LAMERS (University of Oslo)
Welcome and introduction

Published Texts of Italian Fascism and German National Socialism

Chair | Magnus PHARAO HANSEN (University of Copenhagen)

08:50 Christian HARTMANN (Bundeswehr Centre for Military History and Social Sciences)
'Defusing Hitler: The Political Context and the Methodological Concept of the Critical Edition of *Mein Kampf*'

09:20 Han LAMERS (University of Oslo) & Bettina REITZ-JOSSE (University of Groningen)
'Dangerous Documents: Editing Latin Texts of Italian Fascism and German National Socialism'

09:50 Discussion

10:15 *Coffee break*

Epigraphical Texts of Fascist Italy and Francoist Spain

Chair | Marie-Laurence HAACK (University of Picardy Jules Verne)

10:30 Flavia MARCELLO (Swinburne University's School of Design and Architecture)
'Aspirations and Illusions of Control: Re-contextualizing Rome's Fascist Epigraphy'

11:00 Antonio DUPLÁ ANSUÁTEGUI (The University of the Basque Country UPV/EHU)
'Towards a Corpus of Latin Francoist Inscriptions: *FRANCISCVS FRANCO, imperator, dux et moderator Hispaniae*'

11:30 Discussion

12:00 *Lunch*

Objects and Audiovisual Materials of Fascist Italy

Chair | Bettina REITZ-JOOSSE (University of Groningen)

13:30 Susanna ARANGIO (University of Ferrara)

'Arte proibita: Collecting and Displaying Fascist Memorabilia in Italy'

14:00 Beatrice FALCUCCI (Pompeu Fabra University, Barcelona)

'Dangerous Collections: Studying, Exhibiting and Curating Fascist Colonial Heritage Today'

14:30 Patrizia CACCIANI (Istituto Luce, Rome) & Gianmarco MANCOSU (University of London)

'Fascist Audiovisual Debris: Ordering and Making Available the 'Dangerous' Materials of the Istituto Luce'

15:00 Discussion

15:40 *Coffee break*

Neo-Fascist Receptions of 'Dangerous Documents' in Europe

Chair | Han LAMERS (University of Oslo)

16:00 Elisabetta CASSINA WOLFF (University of Oslo)

'Riding or Reading the Tiger? Julius Evola and His Controversial Legacy'

16:30 Discussion

16:45 *Coffee break*

17:00 Plenary discussion

This workshop is organized by the research initiative 'Language Myths: Towards a Global Approach to the Politicization of Ancient Languages' (University of Oslo, University of Copenhagen, and University of Picardy Jules Verne), financed by the Fondation Maison des Sciences de l'Homme and the Centre Universitaire de Norvège à Paris, in collaboration with the research projects 'New Signs of Antiquity' (University of Oslo), funded by the Research Council of Norway (Grant No. 316016), and 'Anchoring the Fascist Revolution' (University of Groningen), supported by OIKOS, the National Research School in Classical Studies in the Netherlands (Gravitation Grant research agenda Anchoring Innovation).

Conveners: Han Lamers (University of Oslo), Bettina Reitz-Joosse (University of Groningen), Marie-Laurence Haack (University of Picardy Jules Verne), Magnus Pharo Hansen (University of Copenhagen).

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